

“ADVANCING DRUG DESIGN WITH PYRAZOLE AND PYRAZOLINE SCAFFOLDS: MULTIFUNCTIONAL PHARMACOLOGICAL PROSPECTS”

Sharanabasav B. Biradar^{1*}, Bharatesh S. Kittur¹, Prasad V. Malagi¹, Guruprasad S. Chilakantmath¹, Sammed Melavanaki¹, Saiprasad H. Masaraddi¹

^{1*}Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry BVV'S Hanagal Shri Kumareshwar College of Pharmacy Bagalkote 587-101 Karnataka, India.

Article Received on
27 August 2025,

Revised on 15 Sept. 2025,
Accepted on 05 Oct. 2025,

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17311726>

***Corresponding Author
Sharanabasav B. Biradar**

Department of
Pharmaceutical Chemistry
BVV'S Hanagal Shri
Kumareshwar College of
Pharmacy Bagalkote 587-
101 Karnataka, India.

ABSTRACT

Pyrazole is a five-membered nitrogen containing heterocyclic scaffold widely recognized for its significant Pharmacological potential. The growing interest in Pyrazole-based molecules has driven the discovery of numerous biologically active molecules. This review outlines the diverse synthetic strategies employed for the synthesis of various substituted Pyrazole and Pyrazoline hybrid strategies along with their associated biological evaluations. Emphasis is placed on recent advances including clinical studies conducted on Pyrazole and Pyrazoline derivatives between 2020 to 2025 aiming to elucidate their mechanism of action and Pharmacological potential.

KEYWORDS: Pyrazoles, Pyrazolines, Heterocyclic compounds, Anti-inflammatory, Analgesic, Anti diabetics, Darovasertib, Zelenirstat.

1. INTRODUCTION

Heterocycles are ring systems in which one or more atoms are heteroatoms such as nitrogen, sulphur and oxygen that replaces carbon atoms within the ring.^[1] Nitrogen-containing heterocycles are widely distributed as a key framework in a vast library of heterocycles, with numerous applications in natural science and other fields of study.^[2] Pyrazoles are a valuable N-heterocyclic scaffold in medical research.^[3] They consist of five membered ring systems containing two nitrogen atoms, one of which is a proton acceptor and the other a proton

donor.^[4] The slightly reduced forms of Pyrazole are known as Pyrazolines, as shown in **Figure 1**, while the entirely reduced form is Pyrazolidine.^[5] Pyrazoles, as stable compounds, become more soluble in organic solvents and have higher boiling temperatures as the number of alkyl groups on their carbon's increases. Pyrazolines are typically basic liquids with high boiling temperatures and little solubility in water.^[6] Numerous strategies for synthesising various Pyrazole and Pyrazoline derivatives have been identified in the scientific literatures.^[7] Furthermore, Pyrazoles have a variety of biological actions such as anti-inflammatory, analgesic, anticancer, and antifungal properties.^[8] Various marketed drugs containing pyrazole nucleus are Antipyrine (Analgesic and antipyretic), Metamizole or Dipyrone (Analgesic and antipyretic), Aminopyrine or Aminopyrine (Anti-inflammatory, analgesic and antipyretic), Phenylbutazone (Osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, spondylitis), Sulfapyrazole (chronic gout), and oxyphenbutazone (antipyretic, gout), which are summarized in **Figure 2**.^[9]

2. EXPLORATION OF PRECEDENT SYNTHETIC METHODOLOGIES GENERAL METHODS OF PREPARATION OF PYRAZOLES AND PYRAZOLINES

Pyrazoles are also referred to as 1,2-diazoles since they contain two nearby nitrogen atoms. Knorr synthesised the first Pyrazole-derived organic compound in 1883. The earliest reports described the condensation reactions involving hydrazines with 1,3-dicarbonyl substrates (**Scheme 1**).^[11] Firstly, Pyrazoles were obtained from decarboxylation of Pyrazole 3,4,5 tri-carboxylic acid. Pyrazoles were first defined by Buchner in 1889 (**Scheme 2**). These early discoveries established the foundation for later developments in Pyrazole chemistry.^[12] The considerable attempt for synthesis of natural Pyrazoline derivatives which was isolated by Japanese workers in 1994. In tropical Asia, *Houttuynia cordata* was isolated from 3n-nonyl Pyrazole, a plant belonging to the "piperaceae" family, and its antibacterial properties were noted. Levo- β -(1-pyrazolyly) alanine is another naturally occurring Pyrazoline derivative. Watermelon seeds (*Citrullus vulgaris*) were used to isolate Pyrazolic amino acids. Nowadays, they are recognised as natural Pyrazoline derivatives, and they are shown in (**Scheme 3**). These findings highlighted the biological relevance of Pyrazoles and simulated interest in their synthetic preparation.^[13] Synthetic access to pyrazolines is often achieved by cyclization of chalcones with hydrazine derivatives. In 1998, Powers *et. al.*, have successfully synthesized Pyrazoline derivatives by the reaction of chalcones and phenyl hydrazine hydrochloride in the presence of sodium hydroxide in the absolute ethanol medium at 70 °C which can serve as intermediates for further transformations. Numerous modifications of this approach have been described including reactions with substituted chalcones and use of varying acid or base catalysts (**Scheme 4**).^[14] Partially saturated Pyrazolines can be oxidized into aromatic Pyrazoles. Activated carbon has been reported to act as an active catalyst or as support promoting the oxidation of Pyrazolines and related intermediates to yield Pyrazoles and Pyrimidines in good efficiency. Hantzsch 1,4-dihydropyridines and 1,3,5-trisubstituted Pyrazolines were aromatized with molecular oxygen to the corresponding Pyridines and Pyrazoles in excellent yields which was reported on 2004 (**Scheme 5**).^[15] Transition-metal catalyst have significantly broadened the scope of Pyrazole synthesis. Palladium-catalysed four component couplings, provide an efficient route to structurally diverse pyrazoline derivatives through one pot protocol and the attempt was made in 2005 by a palladium-catalysed four-component coupling of a terminal alkyne, hydrazine (hydroxylamine), carbon monoxide under ambient pressure, and an aryl iodide to yield Pyrazoline and Isoxazole derivatives (**Scheme 6**).^[16]

Scheme-1: Condensation of hydrazines with 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds.

Scheme-2: Decarboxylation of substituted Pyrazolic acids.

Scheme 3: Examples of naturally occurring Pyrazoline derivatives.

Scheme 4: Synthesis of Pyrazolines via condensation and cyclization of chalcones with hydrazines in the presence NaOH in ethanol at 70^oc.

Scheme 5: Aromatization of dihydro Pyridine and trisubstituted Pyrazoline derivatives in presence of molecular oxygen and activated carbon in HOAc at 120^o for 2-2.5 h.

A new approach was reported by levai in 2005 for the synthesis of 3, 5-diaryl-2-pyrazolines by the reaction of chlorochalcones with hydrazine derivatives in acetic acid by refluxing for 3 h affording the desired pyrazolines in good to excellent yields (**Scheme 7**).^[17] 1, 3-Diketones, which were synthesized in situ from ketones and acid chlorides, were converted into pyrazoles by the addition of hydrazine. This method allows a fast and general synthesis of previously inaccessible pyrazoles and synthetically demanding pyrazole-containing fused rings which was reported in 2006 (**Scheme 8**).^[18] Advances in controlling regio chemistry have been reported by adjusting the reaction parameters such as temperature and solvent a highly regioselective pathway was established, favoring the formation of 1-aryl-3,4,5-substituted pyrazoles based on the condensation of 1,3-diketones with arylhydrazines proceeds at room temperature in N, N -dimethylacetamide and furnishes pyrazoles in good yields which was reported in 2006 (**Scheme 9**).^[19] The reaction of diazo(trimethylsilyl)methylmagnesium bromide with aldehydes or ketones gave 2-diazo-2-(trimethylsilyl) ethanols which was established in 2007 (**Scheme 10**), which were applied to the efficient synthesis of di- and trisubstituted pyrazoles via [3+2] cycloaddition reaction with ethyl propiolate or dimethyl acetylenedicarboxylate.^[20] Various 1-acyl-5-hydroxy-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazoles have been reported in 2008 with good yields from the corresponding 2-alkyn-1-ones. The resulting dihydropyrazoles undergo dehydration and iodination in the presence of ICl and Li₂CO₃ at room temperature to provide 1-acyl-4-iodo-1*H*-pyrazoles with enhanced electron density on the ring (**Scheme 11**).^[21] A convenient one-pot method for the synthesis of N -acyl pyrazoles from aryl nucleophiles, di-*tert*-butylazodicarboxylate and 1,3-dicarbonyl or equivalent compounds was reported in the year 2009. This approach offers a straight forward route to N-acylated pyrazoles in good yields with minimum purification step (**Scheme 12**).^[22]

Scheme 7: Schematic representation of synthesis of diaryl-pyrazolines with aid of reflux in the presence of acetic acid.

Scheme 8: Schematic representation of synthesis of Pyrazole containing fused rings.

Scheme 9: Schematic representation of highly regio selective synthesis of substituted Pyrazoles by condensation reaction.

Scheme 10: Schematic route for synthesizing di and tri substituted Pyrazolines.

Copper-catalyzed [3+2] cycloaddition strategy performed in 2011 which enables the efficient synthesis of poly substituted Pyrazoles from phenylhydrazones and dialkyl ethylene dicarboxylates tolerates a range of functionalities, and the corresponding adducts can be obtained. The copper catalysts play a pivotal role in activating the michael acceptor and facilitating the C-N bond formation. This method provides facile access to structurally diverse Pyrazoles adducts under mild and environmentally benign conditions which is represented in **(Scheme 13)**.^[23] A tandem catalytic cross-coupling/electrocyclization was developed in 2011 for synthesizing 3,4,5-trisubstituted Pyrazoles. Enol triflates react with diazoacetates using Pd (PPh₃)₄ (5mol%) and NMM in DMF at room temperature(3-6hrs), followed by 60 °C (12-18hrs) affording pyrazoles with high structural complexity **(Scheme 14)**.^[24] An unprecedented Ru (II)-catalysed intramolecular oxidative C-N coupling of alkenyl hydrazones was reported in 2012, facilitating the highly substituted Pyrazoles under mild conditions which is demonstrated in **(Scheme 15)**.^[25] In 2013, simple, highly efficient, 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of diazo compounds and alkynyl bromides was reported, affording 3,5-diaryl-4-bromo-3H- pyrazoles or their isomerized counterparts, 3,5-diaryl-4-bromo-1H-pyrazoles in good yields **(Scheme16)**. The diazo intermediates and alkynyl bromides were generated in-situ from tosylhydrazones and gem-dibromo alkenes respectively. This synthetic methodology demonstrated high regioselectivity and excellent functional group tolerance.^[26] A Pt-catalyzed^[3,3] sigmatropic rearrangement/cyclization of propargyl hydrazones efficiently

synthesizes highly functionalized pyrazoles (**Scheme 17**). This method provides a straightforward route to Pyrazoles with diverse substituents, offering valuable intermediates for drug discovery and materials sciences.^[27] A ⁿBu₃P-catalyzed desulfonylative [3 + 2] cycloadditions of allylic carbonates with arylazo sulfones were reported in 2015, enable the synthesis of Pyrazole derivatives this reaction facilitates the formation of Pyrazole ring by activating allylic carbonates to undergo a [3+2] cycloaddition with arylazo sulfone, leading to the formation of highly functionalized Pyrazoles (**Scheme 18**).^[28] Aluminum chloride mediated reactions of *N*-alkylated tosylhydrazones and terminal alkynes was reported in 2016, and they provide a series of 1,3,5-trisubstituted Pyrazoles in very good yields with complete regioselectivity. The protocol is applied to a wide range of substrates and demonstrates excellent functional group tolerance (**Scheme 19**).^[29] Regiochemical control of the cyclo condensation reaction of β-enamino diketones with arylhydrazines reported in 2017 enables one-pot procedures for highly regioselective synthesis of 3,5-disubstituted 4-formyl-*N*-arylpyrazoles or 3, 5-disubstituted 4-hydroxymethyl-*N*-arylpyrazoles (**Scheme 20**). Structural modifications in the β-enamino diketone system allied to the Lewis acid carbonyl activator BF₃ were strategically employed for this control.^[30]

A streamlined one-pots synthetic approach involving the condensation of ketones, aldehydes, and hydrazine monohydrochloride was reported in 2018, facilitating the formation of Pyrazoline intermediates under mild reaction conditions (**Scheme 21**). Subsequent in situ oxidation using bromine enabled the efficient generation of a diverse array of pyrazole derivatives with excellent yields. Alternatively, a greener oxidative protocol by utilizing DMSO under an oxygen atmosphere afforded 3,5-disubstituted or 3,4,5-trisubstituted Pyrazoles via thermal treatment of Pyrazolines, highlighting the methods operational simplicity and environmental compatibility.^[31] A silver-mediated [3 + 2] cycloaddition of *N*-isocyanoiminotriphenylphosphorane as "CNN" building block to terminal alkynes provides Pyrazoles which is effortlessly reported in 2019. The phosphorane reagent, characterized by its bench stability, non-volatility, and lack of odor, serve as a user-friendly isocyanide surrogate. The protocol exhibits broad substrate tolerance, functional group compatibility, and proceeds under mild conditions, thereby offering a versatile and efficient route for pyrazole construction (**Scheme 22**).^[32] *N*-arylpyrazoles can be generated in very high yields by a palladium-catalyzed coupling of aryl triflates with pyrazole derivatives utilising *t*BuBrettPhos as a ligand. For the synthesis of further *N*-arylpyrazole derivatives, the coupling products of 3-trimethylsilylpyrazole provided a helpful template (**Scheme 23**).^[33] Cu-catalyzed aerobic oxidative cyclization of β , γ -unsaturated hydrazones was developed in 2020, affording diverse Pyrazole derivatives via a hydrazone radical intermediate and C-C bond cleavage out and it provides a broad range of Pyrazole derivatives. (**Scheme 24**). The reaction is initiated by the formation of a hydrazone radical, followed by cyclization and a concomitant C=C bond cleavage.^[34] It was reported in 2021 that 5-trifluoromethylpyrazoles may be obtained via a regioselective [3 + 2] cycloaddition of hydrazone chlorides using the industrially accessible and environmentally benign feedstock 2-bromo-3,3,3-trifluoropropene (BTP). There are a number of benefits to this catalyst-free transformation, including gentle reaction conditions, high yields, gramme scale applicability, broad substrate scope, and strong functional group tolerance. It is also simple in operation (**Scheme 25**).^[35] Iodine catalyses a cascade reaction involving enaminones, hydrazines, and DMSO in the presence of Select fluor to produce 1,4-disubstituted Pyrazoles (**Scheme 26**). DMSO serves as both the C1 source and the reaction medium. Furthermore, the synthesis of 1,3,4-trisubstituted Pyrazoles employing aldehydes as alternative C1 building blocks has been performed.^[36] A copper-promoted aerobic oxidative [3+2] cycloaddition of *N*, *N*-disubstituted hydrazines with alkynoates was developed in 2023 provides various substituted Pyrazoles in good yields under basic conditions (**Scheme 27**). In this transformation, inexpensive Cu₂O serves as the

promoter and air acts as the green oxidant. This convenient reaction exhibits high atom, step economy, and regioselectivity.^[37] A facile one-pot (3 + 2) cycloaddition-isomerization-oxidation sequence employing 2,2,2-trifluorodiazoethane and styryl derivatives was successfully exhibited in the same year 2023, 5-aryl-3-trifluoromethyl Pyrazoles afforded good yields under mild conditions. The reaction tolerates a broad variety of functional groups (**Scheme 28**).^[38] Hypervalent iodine (III) reagent have emerged as powerful, eco-friendly oxidants in modern organic synthesis due to their high reactivity and low toxicity. In recent studies iodine (III)-mediated oxidative transformation have been effectively applied to the direct functionalization of electron rich heterocycles, including Pyrazoles and Isoxazoles. Under mild conditions iodine (III) catalyzed synthesis of fully functionalized NH-Pyrazoles and Isoxazoles from α , β -unsaturated hydrazones and oximes was carried out and successfully reported in 2024 (**Scheme 29**) which includes cyclization, 1,2-aryl shift, aromatization, and detosylation. The reaction gives direct access to an advanced intermediate for the preparation of valdecoxib and parecoxib, drugs used for COX-inhibition.^[39] Based on the eutectic point phase diagram, a novel natural deep eutectic solvent (NDES), designated as SER/GLU-DES, was synthesised in 2025 by combining equimolar quantities of serine (SER) and glutaric acid (GLU). The resulting solvent was then analysed using a variety of techniques (**Scheme 30 and 31**). This NDES was subsequently used as an effective and long-lasting catalyst for the synthesis of two series of physiologically important Pyrazolo Pyrano Pyrimidines. The reaction was carried out in a one-pot, four-component condensation involving ethyl acetoacetate, hydrazine hydrate or phenyl hydrazine, barbituric acid, and aldehydes at 700°C in the absence of solvents.^[40]

Scheme 27: Copper (III)-catalysed oxidative cyclization strategy for constructing pyrazole scaffolds under mild aerobic conditions.

Scheme 28: Iodine (III)- mediated oxidative cycloaddition method for trifluoromethyl-substituted pyrazole derivatives.

Scheme 29: Hypervalent iodine-mediated oxidative annulation approach to construct NH-pyrazoles under mild conditions.

Scheme 30: Sketching of SER/GLU-DES.

Scheme 31: Synthesis of 2(a-h) and 2(i-m) by SER/GLU-DES.

3. OVERVIEW OF PHARMACOLOGICAL REVIEW: Pyrazoline derivatives are known to possess broad-spectrum pharmacological activities like antidepressant, anticonvulsant, antimicrobial (such as antibacterial activity and antifungal activity),

antihypertensive activity, antitubercular activity, muscle relaxant, tranquilizing activity, psychoanaleptic activity, antiamoebic activity anti-cancer activity which are reported in various literatures.^[40,41,43]

3.1 CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM (CNS) ACTIVITY: Pyrazolines represent a promising class of central nervous system (CNS)-active heterocycles with demonstrated potential as antidepressant agents. Their mechanism of action involves inhibition of monoamine oxidase- A, serotonin reuptake inhibition, and antioxidant activity, all of which contribute to improved neurotransmitter balance and neuroprotection in depressive states.^[44,46] Structure activity relationship studies have shown that substitutions with electron-donating or halogen groups enhance activity, and hybrid derivatives incorporating chalcone or aryl moieties further improves efficacy.^[45,46] *In vivo* evaluations using behavioral models such as the forced swim test (FST) and tail suspension test (TST) confirm significant antidepressant like compounds.^[44,46] In the quest for novel antidepressant agents, Pyrazolines have emerged as a promising class of compounds. The following research findings highlight their brief review of their approaches and outcomes. Notably, **Natasha Naval Aggarwal *et al.*, (2020)** describe the successful preparation of a series of Pyrazole analogues and evaluated them for CNS-relevant activity consistent with antidepressant models. Structure activity relationship (SAR) analysis revealed that the incorporation of electron-withdrawing substituents at the 3 or 4 -positions of the phenyl ring attached to the Pyrazoline ring core compound (**1a**) significantly enhance anti-depressant activity. A parachloro/parafluoro substituent on the phenyl ring at position three of the Pyrazoline ring dramatically improves antidepressant activity. The addition of electron-donating groups at the second, third, or fourth position of the Pyrazoline phenyl ring reduces antidepressant efficacy, as indicated in the following **Figure 10**.^[47] In comparison to the above work reported, **S. Singh *et al.*, (2021)** devised some of the Pyrazolopyrimidine analogues and all the newly synthesized derivatives were assessed for their *in vivo* and *in vitro* in order to evaluate their Pharmacological activity. Antidepressant activity was assessed using a photoactometer by measuring the locomotor activity of treated animals' models. Compound **2a-b** have shown significant antidepressant activity which is illustrated in **Figure 11**.^[48] Following the initial synthesis and biological review of pyrazolo pyrimidine derivatives further research was expanded by **Xiang-Yang Ye *et al.*, (2023)** synthesized N-(4-(3-(3,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-1H-pyrazol-5-yl) benzyl)-2-morpholinoethan-1-amine pyrazolines analogues. An *in vivo* study indicated that compound **3** exhibited antidepressant-like effects in sucrose preference forced swimming tests, which may

be attributed to the activation of cAMP-dependent signaling. Thus, their experiments demonstrated that a PDE4 inhibitor produced from resveratrol may be effective for the treatment of depression, with following attempts on additional Ongoing attempts to optimise compound 3 which are expected to provide more powerful and selective PDE4 inhibitors, as shown in **Figure 12**.^[49] After the significant findings from the above work, **Dinesh Rishipathak *et al.*, (2024)** synthesized Dihydropyrazolyl-thiazoline-4-one Derivatives and studied antidepressant activity. The promising results of compound **4a**;2-[3-(furan2-yl)-5-(4-dimethylamino-phenyl)-4,5-dihydro 1Hpyrazol-1-yl]-1,3-thiazol-4(5H)-one and compound **4b**;2-[3-(furan-2-yl)-5-(2-chlorophenyl)-4,5-dihydro 1Hpyrazol-1-yl]-1,3-thiazol-4(5H)-one has shown the percentage preference for open arm was 15.11 and 14.17 seconds, with an average time spent in open arm of 45.33 and 42.50 seconds, as shown in **Figure 13**, resulting in a strong anxiolytic effect as compared to control. These chemicals may serve as possible leads for the development of innovative therapeutic treatments targeting anxiety disorders.^[50] In continuation of the aforesaid discoveries, **Elmira K. Hakobyan *et al.*, (2025)** reported the efficient synthesis of new 5-Piperazinopyrazolo[3,4-c]-2,7-naphthyridines and isoxazole [5,4-c]-2,7-naphthyridine fragments the compounds were obtained in good yield and were investigated for neuroprotective properties relevant to CNS/antidepressant research. Thus, the most active compounds in the pentylenpotetrazole test are 5a, 5b, and 5c, with compound **5a** (as depicted in **Figure 14** and its substituents in **Table 1**) having the greatest therapeutic index (greater than 33.6) and an ED₅₀ of 23.8. On the other hand, these simultaneously demonstrated psychotropic (anxiolytic, antidepressant, or sedative) or behavioural depressive effects.^[51]

Figure 14: Structure of synthesized compound 5a.

Table 1: List of functional substituents.

Compd	R	R ¹
5a	Bn	CH(Ph) ²

3.2 ANTICONVULSANT ACTIVITY: Pyrazolines have emerged as a structurally diverse class of heterocyclic compounds with considerable promise as anticonvulsant agents. Preclinical studies have demonstrated that numerous Pyrazoline derivatives exhibit significant seizure-suppressing activity in standard experimental models, such as the maximal electroshock (MES) test and pentylenetetrazol (PTZ)-induced models.^[52,54] Their mechanisms of action are believed to involve modulation of GABAergic neurotransmission, voltage-gated sodium channel inhibition and anti-oxidant effects, all of which contribute to neuronal stabilization and elevation of seizure threshold.^[52,53] Structure activity relationship analyses have indicated that substitution with electron-withdrawing groups (e.g., -Cl, NO₂) and heteroaryl rings enhances anticonvulsant potency and improves Pharmacokinetic behavior.^[52,54] Collectively, these support the potential of Pyrazolines as lead scaffolds in the development of novel antiepileptic agents. Nonetheless further mechanistic elucidation, toxicological assessment and clinical validation are required to fully realize their therapeutic applicability. Multiple research groups have synthesized and evaluated various Pyrazoline derivatives for anticonvulsant activity. According to the study conducted by **Nadeem Siddiqui *et.al.*, (2019)** a series of 2-Pyrazoline derivatives were devised and evaluated for anticonvulsant activity. Among these several analogues (**6a-d**) which are represented in **Figure 15** and their respective substituents in **Table 2** demonstrated complete seizure protection at a dose of 100 mg/kg in preclinical models, administered over a period of 0.5 hours and these compounds warrant further investigations to elucidate their mechanism of action.^[55] Next phase of the review **R. Kerzare *et.al.*, (2020)** reported the synthesis of Indole linked Pyrazoles which are exhibiting anti-convulsant properties. The evaluation of these compounds using the maximal electroshock seizures (MES) model demonstrated that derivatives bearing electron-withdrawing substituents-specifically compounds (**7a-f**) which include chloro, nitro and benzyloxy groups positioned at ortho and para-positions of the phenyl ring attached to the Pyrazoline ring exhibited enhanced activity with a high protection index (PI) as depicted in **Figure 16** and their substituent groups detailed in **Table 3**.^[56] While **Harsh Bhardwaj *et.al.*, (2022)** reported some series of 4-(4,5-diphenyl-1H-imidazol-2-yl)-3,1-substituted phenyl-1H-Pyrazole derivatives which were examined for both anticonvulsant and analgesic activity by using maximal electroshock-induced seizure (MES) method and

Cayman colorimetric based human cyclooxygenase assay kit respectively. Physical and analytical parameters of the newly synthesized Imidazole incorporated Pyrazole derivatives were confirmed by TLC, IR, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR and elemental analysis. In subsequent biological evaluations compound **8a-c** (as depicted in **Figure 17** and their substituents detailed in **Table 4**) showed significant anti-convulsion activity, while the same series of compounds **8a-c** also exhibited notable analgesic effects as compared to other tested derivatives.^[57] In continuing perspectives **Salahuddin *et al.*, (2023)** undertook the design, diversifying the further study and synthesized as set of (3,5-disubstituted pyrazolyl) -(4-chlorophenyl) methanone analogues and screened for anticonvulsant activity and docking studies. In that Compounds **9a-c** were found to be most potent and promising against convulsions at minimum dose of 50mg/kg as reflected in **Figure 18**.^[58]

Fig. 15: Structure of synthesized compound 6a.

Table 2: List of functional substituents.

Compd	R	R ¹
6a	H	Phenyl
6b	2-NO ₂	Phenyl
6c	NO ₂	Phenyl

Figure 16: Structure of synthesized compound 7.

Table 3: List of functional substituents.

Compd	Ar
7a	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -
7b	4-C ₆ H ₅ -CH ₂ O- C ₆ H ₄ -
7c	4-(CH ₃) ₂ -N- C ₆ H ₄ -
7d	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄
7e	2,4-(Cl ₂)-C ₆ H ₃
7f	4-NO ₂ - C ₆ H ₄ -

Table 4: List of functional substituents.

Compound	R	R ^I
8a	4-OH	2,4-(NO ₂) _{2s}
8b	3-NO ₂	2,4-(NO ₂) ₂
8c	4-Br	2,4-(NO ₂) ₂

3.3 ANTI-INFLAMMATORY AND ANALGESIC ACTIVITY: Pyrazoline represent a promising class of heterocyclic compounds with substantial anti-inflammatory and analgesic potential. Numerous studies have demonstrated their efficacy in suppressing inflammation and pain through mechanisms involving cyclooxygenase (COX-1 and COX-2) inhibition,

nitric oxide (NO) suppression and down regulation of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-6.^[59,60] Structural characteristics, such as electron-drawing groups (eg., -Cl, -NO₂) on the aryl moieties and the inclusion of heterocyclic substitutions, have been observed to boost both inflammatory and analgesic efficacy, probably by improving enzyme binding affinity and bioavailability.^[60,61] Some derivatives have demonstrated action comparable to aspirin.^[59,61] Furthermore, Pyrazolines exert their analgesic effects via both peripheral and cerebral pathways, which may involve regulation of opioid receptors and suppression of prostaglandin synthesis. These results suggest that Pyrazolines and Pyrazoles are attractive lead scaffolds for the design of dual acting anti-inflammatory analgesic agents. Encouraged by the above citations the **Adnan A. Bekhit *et al.*, (2022)** developed Pyrazole-based benzene sulphonamide which exhibited both anti-inflammatory and analgesic activity in Pharmacological testing. Compound **10a** demonstrated significant antiinflammatory and analgesic effects, surpassing those of the two standard reference drugs, **Indomethacin and Celecoxib**. In contrast compound **10b** showcased lower COX-2 selectivity than Celecoxib which is reflected in **Figure 19**, indicating the potential involvement of other alternative anti-inflammatory mechanisms, moreover compound **10b** may offer improved cardiovascular safety relative to conventional selective COX-2 inhibitors.^[62] Following the initial synthesis and biological evaluations of previous review **Mostafa M. M. El-Miligy *et al.*, (2022)** designed thymol–pyrazole hybrids that displayed anti-inflammatory activity and ulcerogenic activity. Among the synthesized derivatives Compound **11a** demonstrated the highest inhibitory activity, surpassing the reference drugs **Celecoxib and Diclofenac sodium** as illustrated in **Figure 20**. These findings highlight the potential of thymol-based scaffolds as promising lead compounds for the development of safer and more effective anti-inflammatory therapeutics.^[63] In the continuation of the previous review **Dimitra Hadjipavlou-Litina *et al.*, (2022)** investigated Pyrazole and Pyrazoline derivatives in oxidative burst assays using human leukocytes, identifying compounds that reduced inflammatory responses and indicated antioxidant-related anti-inflammatory activity. In the DPPH assay, the novel derivatives demonstrated moderate antioxidant activity with variations depending on time and concentration. Among the tested compounds **12a** and **12b** exhibited moderate reduction of the ABTS radical cation (ABTS \pm) at concentration 100 μ M, All the tested compounds however significantly inhibited lipid peroxidation. Lipophilicity was found to play an important role in this activity. Compound **12c** showed the highest lipoxygenase inhibitory activity in competitive mode. Molecular Docking studies suggest that

12c may interact in an allosteric manner, involving hydrophobic interactions with **VAL126**, **PHE143**, **VAL520** and **LYS526** as well as halogen bond between the chlorine atom and **ARG182**. Compounds **12d-e** demonstrated the most potent anti-inflammatory activities and also exhibited satisfactory analgesic activity, whereas **12d** was effective in reducing the severity and the onset of adjuvant-induced arthritis. The structure of compound **12** and its substituents are accompanied in **Figure 21**.^[64] Building upon prior research **Ahlam M. Abdallah et. al., (2024)** developed hybrid Pyrazole scaffolds that attenuated ameliorate synovial inflammation in collagen-induced arthritis mice model. These compounds function via targeting the p38 MPK and COX-2 signaling pathways. Among the synthesized compounds, compound **13** demonstrated significant reduction in arthritic score and the inflammatory cytokine expression, it also improved synovitis histopathology, and ameliorated oxidative stress in the CIA mice model, suggesting its therapeutic potential through modulation of **p38MAPK and COX-2**.^[65] Recent studies by **Sonia Rocha et. al., (2024)** led to the design and synthesis of some Pyrazoline derivatives to enhance anti-inflammatory activity. Among the tested compounds, only compound **14** exhibited a marked decrease in cell viability at 25 μM as depicted **Figure 22**, while erythrocyte viability remained unaffected at 12.5 μM . Structural analysis indicated that specific moieties contributed to enhanced biological activity. Notably the presence of an unsubstituted **4-(chlorostyryl)** group at N-1 aromatic ring and the incorporation of the **3-[2-(4-methoxyphenyl) naphthalen-1-yl]** substituent on the on the Pyrazol scaffold favorable features for reducing PGE2 level. Furthermore, the inclusion of **nitro groups** and **4-(4-chlorostyryl) group** on the Pyrazoline enhanced CO inhibition and suppressed oxidative burst in human leukocytes.^[66] Exploring the Isatin and Indole scaffolds **Ashraf S. Hassan et.al., (2025)** introduced additional Pyrazole–Isatin and Pyrazole–Indole Conjugates, several of which showed anti-inflammatory efficacy in experimental screening, reinforcing the therapeutic promise of pyrazole scaffolds for inflammatory disorders. Among these compound **15b** exhibited (as illustrated in **Figure 23**) potent inhibition against COX-1, COX-2, and 5-LOX enzymes with an IC₅₀ of 5.44 ± 0.03 , 5.37 ± 0.04 , and 7.52 ± 0.04 , respectively, values comparable to those of standard antiinflammatory agents **Indomethacin** and **Zileuton**. Computational toxicity predictions classified both series as class IV ($300 < \text{LD}_{50} \leq 2000$). The Molecular lipophilicity potential (MLP) mapping suggested that compound **15b** (as illustrated in **Figure 24**) exhibited lipophilic surface properties conducive to membrane permeability enhancing therapeutic potential. Furthermore, topological polar surface area

(TPSA) calculations revealed that all conjugates possess a TPSA value exceedingly more than 140 \AA^2 suggesting favorable intestinal absorption profiles.^[67]

Figure 19: E-4-[3-(4-methylphenyl)-5-hydroxyiminomethyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl] benzene sulfonamide (compound 10).

Figure 20: Thymol based pyrazole hybrid (compound 11).

Figure 21: Structure of synthesized compound 12 and their respective substituent functionalities.

Figure 22: Structure of synthesized compound 14 (4 styryl pyrazoles).

Figure 23: Structure of synthesized compound 15a pyrazole -Isatin conjugates.

Figure 24: Structure of synthesized compound 15b pyrazole -Indole conjugates.

3.4 ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY: Pyrazoles and Pyrazolines evinced as key Pharmacophores in the search for novel anti-microbial agents due to their structural versatility and broad-spectrum activity. Numerous derivatives within these classes have demonstrated potent anti-bacterial and anti-fungal properties against both gram-positive and gram - negative bacterial strains as well as pathogenic fungi such as *candida albicans* and *aspergillus niger*.^[68,69,70] Their antimicrobial effects are believed to result from mechanisms such as inhibition of microbial enzymes, disruption of membrane integrity and interference with nucleic acid synthesis. Substitution at key positions on the Pyrazole and Pyrazoline

rings- nitro and electron donating moieties have been shown to significantly enhance antimicrobial potency.^[69,70] Given the risen threat of antimicrobial resistance Pyrazole and Pyrazoline scaffolds offer a valuable foundation for the development of next-generation antimicrobial therapeutics. However, more research on their toxicity profiles, resistance mechanisms, and *in vivo* efficacy is required before to clinical translation. **Asad *et al.*, (2020)** utilized propionic acid and hydrazine hydrate to synthesise a series of N-propionyl 2-pyrazolines from chalcones. All recently synthesised compounds were subjected to antibacterial screening against gram-positive bacterial strain (*B. subtilis*, *S. Aureus*) and gram-negative bacterial strain (*E. Coli*, *P. Peli*). The structural organisation of these compounds (**16**) represented in **Figure 25**, which displayed substantial excellent antibacterial activity.^[71] **Begum evranos aksoz *et.al.*, (2020)** synthesised a variety of Pyrazoline and one hydrazone derivatives and tested them for antibacterial and antifungal characteristics to further examine their pharmacological implications. Antimicrobial efficacy was tested against two Gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli* ATCC 25922 and *P. aeruginosa* ATCC 27853), three Gram-positive bacteria (*S. aureus* ATCC 29213, *Efaecalis* ATCC 29212, and *B. subtilis* ATCC 6633), and a fungus (*C. albicans* ATCC 10231) using ampicillin, ofloxacin, and fluconazole as the standard drugs. Compounds **17ab** showed the strongest antibacterial activity against *E. faecalis*, with a minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of 32 µg/ml. The molecular structures and substituent information of these compounds are shown in **Figure 26** and **Table 5**.^[72] To evaluate the therapeutic potential of newly synthesized pyrazoline derivatives their antimicrobial activities were assessed and reported by **Fatih TOK *et.al.*, (2022)** Ciprofloxacin was employed as a standard reference drug for comparison. All the synthesized pyrazoline derivatives exhibited significant anti-bacterial activity particularly against *enterococcus faecalis* (ATC 29212) and *candida glabrata* (ATCC 90030). Several compounds **18a-b** displayed noteworthy inhibitory effects against tested bacterial and fungal strains exhibited the lowest minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values indicating superior antimicrobial efficacy as depicted in **Figure 27**.^[73] **Zeyad D. Najmuldeen *et.al.*, (2023)** investigated further by designing a variety of Pyrazoline incorporating sulphonamide groups, which revealed promising antimicrobial activity, suggesting the benefit of combining these Pharmacophores. The antibacterial potential of these substances was tested using the agar well diffusion experiment. The *in vitro* antimicrobial spectrum included tests against the fungus strain candida albicans, gram-positive bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*) and gram-negative bacteria (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*). Structure-activity relationship (SAR) analysis indicated that compounds

bearing electron-donating substituents such as $-OCH_3$ and $-N(CH_3)_2$ exhibited enhanced activity against gram-positive strains. Conversely derivatives with strong electron-withdrawing groups like $-Cl$ and $-NO_2$ demonstrated pronounced activity against gram-negative pathogens. Among the synthesized derivatives compound **19** (Illustrated in Figure 28) exhibited the most significant zone of inhibition across all strains suggesting broad spectrum efficacy. Remarkably its antifungal efficacy surpassed that of the standard reference drug **fluconazole** highlighting potential for further development as a dual action antimicrobial candidate.^[74] **Krupa Prajapatia *et al.*, (2024)** reported Pyridine-Thiophene clubbed Pyrazolines hybrids and screened for their anti-microbial activities. It was important to highlight that three of these derivatives **20a-c** displayed superior antibacterial activity than the standard medications as attributed to their structural features and substituent groups in **Fig 29 and Table 6**. Furthermore, Molecular docking studies were conducted targeting the functioning site of the KS-AT domains of *Mycobacterial Pks13 enzyme*. These studies revealed well-clustered binding conformations with binding affinities ranging from -10.5 to -9.8 kcal/mol. The most active compound **20 d** exhibited highest binding score of -10.5 kcal/mol as determined using PYRX Autodock VINA. This score indicates favorable accommodation of compound 20 d at the active site of the PKs enzyme, facilitated by both network of bonded and non-bonded interactions.^[75]

Figure 25: Structure of Synthesized Compound 16.

Figure 26: Structure of synthesized compound 17.

Table 5: List of functional substituents.

Compd	R ¹	R ²	R ³	R ⁴	R ⁵	R ⁶	R ⁷	R ⁸
17a	-OH	-H	-H	-Br	-H	-H	-OCH ₃	Pyridin-4yl
17b	-OH	-H	-OCH ₃	-H	-H	-H	-Br	Pyridin-4yl

Compound 18a Ar= cyanophenyl

Compound 18b Ar= Dimethyl amino(phenyl)

Figure 27: Structure of synthesized compound 18.

Figure 28: Structure of 2-(5-(4-nitrophenyl)-3-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)-N-(4-sulfonyl phenyl) acetamide (Compound 19).

Figure 29: Structure of synthesized compound 20.

Table 6: List of Functional Substituents.

Compound	R
20a	Methyl phenyl
20b	Bromo phenyl
20c	Flouro phenyl

3.5 ANTI-TUBERCULAR ACTIVITY: Pyrazole and Pyrazoline derivatives afforded significant scaffolds in the development of novel anti-tubercular agents. Their structural versatility enables effective inhibition of mycobacterium tuberculosis through various mechanisms including the targeting of inhA and DprE1 enzymes. Recent studies have

highlighted that substitution with electron withdrawing group and heteroaryl moieties enhance their antimycobacterial efficacy.^[76,77] Several compounds have exhibited MIC values comparable to or better than standard drugs like isoniazid supporting their potential as lead candidates in antitubercular drug discovery.^[76,77,78] **Mohamad Nurul Azmi *et. al.*, (2021)** devised a library of novel 3,5-disubstituted-Pyrazoline derivatives and tested them for anti-tubercular efficacy. *In vitro* research against *Mycobacterium TB H37Ra* was used to assess the anti-tuberculosis activity of the synthesised compounds. Among the synthesised compound **21a** showed the strongest inhibitory effect against *M. tuberculosis H37Ra* with a minimum inhibitory dose of 34 μ M. Molecular docking analysis suggested that compound **21a** (reflected in **Figure 30**) demonstrated better binding affinity to the **cytochrome P450 14 alpha-sterol demethylase (CYP51) complex**, indicating a potential mode of action through enzyme inhibition.^[79] **Venkatesan Jayaprakash *et.al.*, (2021)** fabricated some Pyrazoline based **Mycobactin**, a siderophore involved in iron acquisition by *M. tuberculosis*. Among these Compounds **22a and 22b** exhibited the most potent Mtb (IC₅₀ = 47 M, MIC = 16 μ M) among the active DAP derivatives as their structures are represented in **Figure 31**. Interestingly majority of active compounds demonstrated anti-tubercular efficacy in both iron-depleted (**GAST**) and iron-replete (**GAST + Fe**) media. This observation suggests compounds targets of these compounds are involved in mycobacterial process critical in both low and high-iron environments.^[80] Further analysis revealed by **Mayursinh Zala *et.al.*, (2023)** developed some Pyrazolyl- Pyrazoline conjugates incorporating triazole and tetrazole motifs. These hybrids were evaluated for their anti-tubercular activity. The majority of the derivatives were produced in good yields with high purity. Notably, inclusion of electron-withdrawing and donating groups in compounds **23a-d** resulted in excellent antitubercular activity as shown in **Figure 32** and their substituents in **Table 7**. Molecular docking experiments further suggested that these hybrids could interact favorably with the active site of InhA enzyme engaging in substantial bonded and non-bonded interactions.^[81] To deepen the understanding of this activity **Krupa Prajapati *et.al.*, (2024)** derived some Pyridine-Thiophene clubbed Pyrazoline hybrids and evaluated them for their antimicrobial and anti-tubercular activity. Notably, three derivatives **24a-c** exhibited superior antibacterial and antitubercular activities compared to the standard medications as depicted in **Figure 33** and their resultant substituents summarized in **Table 8**. Furthermore, Molecular docking studies were conducted targeting the ketos synthesis-acyltransferase (KS-AT) domains of *Mycobacterial Pks13* enzyme. These studies revealed well- clustered binding poses with

binding affinities ranging from -10.5 to -9.8 kcal/mol indicating strong interactions between the compounds and the enzyme active site.^[82]

Table 7: List of Functional Substituents.

Compd	R	Hydrazine Derivative	X
23a			S

23b		O	
23c		S	

Figure 33: Structure of synthesized compound 24.

Table 8: List of functional substituents.

Compound	R
24a	Methyl phenyl
24b	Bromo phenyl
24c	Flouro phenyl

3.6 ANTICANCER ACTIVITY: Pyrazoles and Pyrazolines emerged as potent scaffolds in the development of anticancer agents due to their ability to interact involved in tumor progression and cell proliferation. A wide array of derivatives have demonstrated significant cytotoxicity against various human cancer cell lines, including breast (**MCF-7**) lung (**A549**), colon (**HT-29**) and cervical (**HeLa**) cancers.^[83,84,85] These compounds exert their anticancer effects via mechanisms such as tubulin polymerization inhibition, DNA intercalation kinase inhibition (e.g., **EGFR**, **VEGFR**, **CDKS**), and induction of apoptosis through caspase activation and mitochondrial membrane depolarization.^[84,85] Structural modifications such as aryl or heteroaryl substitution at specific ring positions, introduction of electron withdrawing groups and hybridization with other Pharmacophores- have led to significantly enhanced selectivity and potency.^[84,85] Some analogs have shown IC₅₀ values comparable to standard chemotherapeutics agents like Doxorubicin and Cisplatin. Given these promising outcomes Pyrazole and Pyrazoline derivatives represent a valuable source of novel anticancer candidates. However further *in vivo* validation, toxicity profiling and mechanistic elucidation are required before clinical translation can be achieved. To assess the flow therapeutic

potential **Dimitris Matiadis *et.al.*, (2020)** crafted some series of Pyrazoline hybrids exhibiting potent anticancer activity. Among the diverse structures, certain recurring structural motifs, substituents and configuration were identified to correlate with enhanced anticancer efficacy. Notably as illustrated by compound **25** in **Figure 34**. In general, *p*-methoxyphenyl groups at the C-3 and C-5 positions of the core ring system were found to increase cytotoxicity. Additionally, the incorporation of a trimethoxy phenyl moiety-an element structurally inspired by combretastatin was frequently associated with improved bioactivity. In parallel investigations electron withdrawing groups, such as fluorine or chlorine substituents were also shown to augment biological activity.^[86] In continuation of the study **Melati Khairuddean *et.al.*, (2022)** reported a series of heterocyclic Pyrazoline hybrids for examining potent anticancer agents. The cytotoxic activity of Pyrazoline derivatives against breast cancer cell lines revealed that compound **26a** is the best-proposed candidate against hormonal breast cancer, while compound **26b** is the most potent against non-hormonal breast cancer as shown in **Figure 35**.^[87]

Artania Adnin Tri Suma1 *et. al.*, (2023) crafted 1-Formyl-2-Pyrazolines and tested their anticancer efficacy. Compound **27** (showcased in **Figure 36**) revealed moderate activity, with the maximum cytotoxicity against Hela cancer cells (IC₅₀ = 25.01 μM) and low activity against WiDr, MCF7, T47D, and 4T1 cancer cells. Furthermore Compound **27** exhibited moderate cytotoxic activity against MCF7 and 4T1 cancer cells (IC₅₀ = 82.87 and 92.70 μM), but not against WiDr, HeLa, or T47D cancer cells.^[88] Recent advancements in medicinal chemistry have been furthered continued by the work of **Bahaa G. M. Youssif** and co-workers, (2024) fabricated a series of new Pyrazole/Pyrimidine-based scaffolds. These compounds were developed using established methodologies aimed at targeting heat shock Protein 90 as potential inhibitors with apoptotic Anti-Breast Cancer Activities as illustrated in **Figure 37** and **38**. Among the synthesized compounds **28a-b** have been identified as the most potent anti-breast cancer agents, exhibiting a substantial inhibition of Hsp90. Compounds **28a-b** exhibited no impact on non-tumor cells MCF-10A, indicating the selective targeting of these compounds towards tumor cells. The apoptotic studies demonstrate that compounds **28a- b** can enhance the expression of proapoptotic markers (**caspase 3, caspase 8, and BAX**) while inhibiting the expression of the anti-apoptotic protein BCL-2. Compound **28a** demonstrated favorable binding affinities with the active sites of Hsp90, as shown by molecular docking and simulation assays. Collectively these findings indicate that **28a-b** are promising **Hsp90 inhibitor** with potential candidates for advancing innovative breast cancer

treatments.^[89] To investigate this further **Hayder R. Fadhil *et al.*, (2024)** crafted some new series of Pyrazoline derivatives and evaluated for breast cancer cell lines. As illustrated in **Figure 39** Compound **29** which exhibited an IC₅₀ value of 2.79 μ M against MDA-MB-468 cell line, corresponding to roughly a 5.4-fold improvement compared with reference **Tamoxifen** which had an IC₅₀ value of 15.29 μ M.^[90] **Rezk R. Ayyad *et al.*, (2024)** reported the synthesis of Pyrazoline derivatives containing a 4-methylsulfonylphenyl moiety. These chemicals were tested for anticancer efficacy against several human cancer cell lines. Compounds **30a -b** demonstrated broad-spectrum anticancer activity against HL-60 (IC₅₀ of 10.43 and 8.99 mM, respectively), MCF-7 (IC₅₀ of 11.70 and 12.48 mM, respectively), and MDA-MB-231 (IC₅₀s of 4.07 and 7.18 mM, respectively). **Compound 30c** demonstrated considerable anticancer activity in the HL-60 and MDA-MB-231 cell lines (IC₅₀ = 8.43 and 12.54 mM, respectively), as well as moderate activity with MCF-7 (IC₅₀ = 16.2 mM). Furthermore, Compounds **30a** and **30b** were found to be efficient **HER2 inhibitors** (IC₅₀ = 0.496 and 0.0253 mM, respectively), when compared to **Erlotinib** (IC₅₀ = 0.085 mM), as depicted in **Figure 40** and their substituent variations in **Table 9**.^[91] In light of these findings, **Amanda-Lee E. Manicum *et al.*, (2025)** established and successfully reported pyrazole-based derivatives as potential cancer agents. Based on the results of anticancer screening, it is clear that none of the substances outperformed the standard medications in the cancer cell lines studied, indicating a significant restriction to this study. Compound **31** showed the most antiproliferative impact against pancreatic (CFPAC-1) cancer (**depicted in Figure 41**) with an IC₅₀ value of 61.7 \pm 4.9 μ M. As a result, additional research, such as the complexation of these ligands with d-group metals (Re, Tc, and Mn), is required to understand their biological activity and assess their potential for future uses in drug discovery and development.^[92]

Figure 35: Structure of synthesized compound 26.

Figure 36: Structure of synthesized compound 27.

Figure 37: Structure of synthesized compound 28a.

Figure 38: Structure of synthesized compound 28b.

Figure 39: Structure synthesized of compound 29.

Table 9: List of substituent functionalities.

Compound	R ₁	R ₂
30a	4-me	4-me
30b	H	OH

3.7 Anti-viral Activity: Pyrazole and Pyrazolines garnered increasing attention as potential antiviral agents due to their structural flexibility and broad-spectrum activity against various viral pathogens. Several derivatives have shown significant inhibitory effects against viruses such as HIV, HCV, Influenza, HSV and SARS-CoV by targeting enzymes like reverse transcriptase, proteases, polymerases and entry glycoproteins.^[93,94,95] Substitution at the C-3 and C-5 positions of the pyrazole ring or incorporation of nitrogen rich heterocycles in pyrazole derivatives has enhanced antiviral efficacy, likely through improved binding interactions and selectivity towards viral targets.^[94,95] Some of the compounds have demonstrated comparable efficacy to standard antivirals such as zidovudine, oseltamivir and ribavirin in *in vitro* assays.^[94] These findings suggest that pyrazoles and pyrazolines possess significant potential for the development of novel antiviral therapies. Nevertheless, further mechanistic profiling and *in vivo* studies are essential to support their therapeutic translation. The significant findings were attempted by **Nikolai O. Vorozhtsov *et al.*, (2021)** devised various series of Pyrazoline salts and assessed their antiviral activity. Among the screened compounds as depicted in **Figure 42** compound **32** identified as 1-bornylidene-3-phenylpyrazolinium tetrafluoroborate derived from (+)-camphor exhibited the highest anti-

viral activity against *influenza A/Puerto Rico/8/34 (H1N1)* virus with an IC₅₀ 6.2 μM and selectivity index of 107. In contrast its corresponding stereoisomer displayed no detectible antiviral activity.^[96] **Malika Berredjem *et al.*, (2021)** conducted Crystallographic studies, biological evaluations and POM/Docking investigations on Pyrazoles-Sulfonamide hybrids (PSH). These studies indicating a combined anti-bacterial and antiviral Pharmacophore features, enabling *in silico* screening for potential anti-Covid-19 activity. Among the derivatives studied, pyrazole-sulfonamide derivatives **33 (a-g)** as depicted in **Figure 43** and their substituent groups (**refer to Table 10**) exhibited significant interactions at **SARS-CoV-2 main protease** binding site. These interactions were comparable to those of the reference ligand RZG, primarily due to similar hydrophobic interactions.^[97] Further investigations conducted by **Vincent A. Obakachi *et al.*, (2021)** led to the fabrication and characterization some 24 novel Pyrazolone derivatives. *In silico* molecular docking studies revealed that compounds (**34a-e**) as illustrated in **Figure 44** along with their respective substituents listed in **Table 11** demonstrated significantly higher binding high affinity towards **SARS-CoV-2 Sgp** and **hACE-2** receptors, relative to the standard reference compounds. These findings indicate Pyrazolone-based compounds have the potential viral entry inhibitors, effectively blocking the interactions between the virus and host cells.^[98] Based on preliminary findings, **Rezan Huseen Hama Salih *et al.*, (2022)** have devised and characterized series of Pyrazoline derivatives as potential inhibitors of the **SARS-CoV-2 main proteas**. Compound **35** which is depicted in **Figure 45** (−8.3 kcal/mol) demonstrated the highest binding affinity **SARS-CoV-2 Mpro** inhibitor among the docked compounds. Furthermore, compound **35** exhibited more favorable ADMET properties compared to the other synthesized derivatives.^[99] Most recently based on a strategic Pharmacological and Synthetic design approach **Ntombenhle H. Gama *et al.*, (2025)** fabricated and evaluated of novel series of 3-benzoylbenzofurans and Pyrazole derivatives for anti-HIV activity. Four compounds, including two 3-benzoylbenzofurans and two Pyrazole derivatives (**designated as 36f and 36h**) demonstrated the most potent inhibitory effects against HIV-1 pseudo virus infections (**Q23 and CAP210**) with IC₅₀ values less than 10 μM (**as reflected in Figure 46**). Notably, compounds **36b** and **36f** were indentified as most potent inhibitors among the 3-benzoylbenzofurans and Pyrazole derivatives respectively.^[100]

Figure 42: Structure synthesized of compound 32 R=Phenyl.

Figure 43: Structure synthesized of compound 33 a-g.

Table 10: List of Functional Substituents.

Compd	33a	33b	33c	33d	33e	33f
R ₁	H	H	4-OCH ₃	4-OCH ₃	4-Cl	4-Cl
R ₂	H	4-Cl	H	4-Cl	H	4-Cl

Figure 44: Structure synthesized of compound 34.

Table 11: List of functional substituents.

Compd	R ¹	R ²
34a	H	Br
34b	H	2,5-OH
34c	H	NO ₂
34d	Cl	Br
34e	Cl	Cl

Figure 45: Structure synthesized of compound 35.

3.8 Antifungal Activity: Pyrazoles and Pyrazolines manifested noteworthy antifungal activity making them promising scaffolds for the development of novel antifungal agents, especially in light of increasing resistance to conventional therapies. Several derivatives have shown significant inhibitory effects against pathogenic fungi such as *Candida albicans*, *aspergillus niger*, *trichophyton rubrum* and *cryptococcus neoformans*.^[101,102,103] Their antifungal action is thought to arise from mechanisms including inhibition of ergosterol biosynthesis, disruption of fungal cell membrane integrity and interference with mitochondrial functions.^[102,103] Substituents such as halogens (e.g., Cl.-F) nitro groups and electron donating groups on aryl rings have been shown to enhance activity likely by increasing lipophilicity and membrane permeability.^[101,102,103] Some Pyrazoline and Pyrazoles have demonstrated minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) comparable to standard antifungals like **Fluconazole and Amphotericin B**. These encouraging findings support the continued investigations of pyrazole and pyrazoline derivatives as effective antifungal candidates. However more extensive safety evaluations are needed to advance them toward clinical applications. In contrast to these above related studies, **Ibrahim F. Nassarb *et.al.*, (2020)** devised a series new Pyrazoline-Based Thiazole derivatives and evaluated their Anti- fungal Activities. Among these, compounds **37a-b** as interpreted in **Figure 47**, highlighted for potent effects against almost all gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria as well as all fungi.^[104] In continuation of previous findings, **Begum evranos aksoz *et.al.*, (2020)** reported the synthesis and biological evaluations of a series of Pyrazoline and hydrazone derivatives for their antifungal properties. Pyrazoline derivatives demonstrated moderate anti-microbial efficacy against the bacteria and fungus. It was noting that structural comparisons revealed that replacing methyl group at the C-5 position of the A ring in place of a methoxy group at the C-4 position of the A ring enhanced the antifungal activity as well as antimicrobial activity against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *E. faecalis*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *C. albicans* compounds **38a-b** as depicted in **Figure 48** and their resulting structural variations detailed in

Table 12.^[105] To explore the further research **Mehlika Dilek Altintop *et.al.*, (2021)** assembled novel series of Bis-pyrazolines Endowed with Potent Antifungal Activity against *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus niger*. According to the data illustrated in **Figure 49**, compounds **39a- b** were found to be active against *C. albicans* (MIC= 0.016 mg/mL) as well as *A. niger* (MIC= 0.008 mg/mL). Furthermore, assay confirmed that these compounds exhibited selective antifungal effects with (IC₅₀ > 0.500 mg/mL for NIH/3T3 cell line) indicating low cytotoxicity.^[106] Further investigations were carried out by **Jie Wang *et.al.*, (2024)** involved the synthesis and structural characterization of 5-phenyl Pyrazoline derivatives and screened for anti-fungal activity. Results from the Fungal inhibition assays showed that the target compounds exhibited significant inhibitory effects against various plant pathogenic fungi.

Among the evaluated compounds target compound **40** which is reflected in **Figure 50** showed notable inhibitory activity against *Rhizoctonia solani* AG1.^[107] Additional investigations were conducted by the **Abdul Rahman Khan *et.al.*, (2024)** crafted and reported 5-(2-Bromo-5Fluorophenyl)-3-(1hPyrrol-2-Yl)-4,5-Dihydro-1H-Pyrazole and tested against three fungal stains including *Candida albicans*, *Candida parapsilosis* and *Candida tropicalis*. As illustrated in **Figure 51** compound **41** demonstrated selective antifungal activity against these strains with inhibitory effects observed at concentrations ranging from 25 to 50 µg/mL. Furthermore, as in *in silico* assessment of compound (41) was performed using the admetSAR tool.^[108] Most recently subsequent investigations carried out by **Basma T. Abd-Elhalim *et.al.*, (2025)** evaluated antifungal activity and biocompatibility assessment of a new series of pyrazole derivatives using the molecular docking and dynamic simulation techniques. The study encompassed twenty pyrazole analogues assessed them for their antifungal potential, with compound **42b** (as revealed in the **Figure 52**) exhibiting the most pronounced activity against *A. niger* and *A. flavus*. Specifically, compound **42b** (refer **Figure 53**) demonstrated 100% antifungal activity and 50% at doses of 250 µg/ml. The biocompatibility of these compounds was validated using HFB4 normal human skin cell line. Molecular docking experiments revealed strong binding affinities of the compounds with essential fungal proteins in fungi, indicating their potential mechanisms to hinder enzyme activity and demonstrate antifungal properties. These findings underscore the significant anti-fungal properties of the Pyrazole derivatives and suggest their promise for further exploration in antifungal drug development.^[109]

Table 12: List of functional substituents.

Compd	38a	38b
R ¹	-OH	-OH
R ²	-H	-H
R ³	-H	-OCH ₃
R ⁴	-CH ₃	-H
R ⁵	-H	-H
R ⁶	-H	-H
R ⁷	-CH ₃	-CH ₃
R ⁸	-Phenyl	-Phenyl

Figure 49: Structure synthesized compound 39 Ar= phenyl, X=S.

Figure 50: Structure synthesized compound 40.

Figure 51: Structure synthesized compound 41.

Figure 52: Structure synthesized compound 42b.

Figure 53: Illustrates observation of the compound 42b with treated pathogenic fungal strains, Zone of inhibition during a 72hr at an Incubation period of 28⁰C.

3.9 Anti-Oxidant activity: Pyrazoles and Pyrazolines exhibited significant antioxidant potential attributed to their ability to scavenge free radicals and modulate oxidative stress pathways. These heterocyclic scaffolds interact with reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS) reducing oxidative damage to biomolecules such as DNA, lipids and proteins.^[110,111,112] The antioxidant activity of Pyrazoles and Pyrazolines is greatly influenced by their structural features-particularly electron donating groups (e.g., -OH, -OCH₃) and conjugated aromatic systems which enhance radical stabilization and hydrogen donating capacity.^[111,112] Compounds bearing phenolic or substituted aryl rings at the C-3 and C-5 positions have shown strong scavenging activity in assays like DPPH, ABTS and FRAP with efficacy in some cases comparable to standard antioxidants such as ascorbic acid and butylated hydroxy toluene (BHT).^[110] These findings support the further exploration of Pyrazole and Pyrazoline derivatives as promising antioxidant agents with therapeutic relevance in diseases associated with oxidative stress including neurodegenerative, cardiovascular and metabolic disorders. In a recent study **Manish Rana *et al.*, (2023)** fabricated and characterized Pyrazole–Pyrazoline hybrid derivatives including compound **43** and evaluated their anti-oxidant potential using the DPPH radical scavenging assay. The antioxidant activity was assessed based on the color change of the DPPH solution from purple to yellow after 1 hr incubation, indicating radical scavenging. This was accompanied by a decrease in absorbance measured at 516nm, confirming the presence of antioxidant moieties. The IC₅₀ value, representing the concentration required to

inhibit 50% of DPPH radicals was determined for the compound by analyzing the dose-dependent antioxidant response. **Ascorbic acid** was used as a standard reference compound for comparison. The IC₅₀ value for compound **43** (as reflected in **Figure 54**) was found to be $1.37 \pm 0.0015 \text{ mg/ml}$.^[113] Based on the promising findings reported by **Salma Mortada et.al., (2024)** a series of pyrazole derivatives were developed and structurally characterized. These compounds were subsequently evaluated for their anti-diabetic and anti-oxidant activity. According to the antioxidant evaluation results (refer to **Figure 55**) compound **44 Pyz-2** demonstrated remarkable antioxidant potential. The compound exhibited significant free radical scavenging activity, indicating that the designed molecule possesses considerable antioxidant and radical neutralizing capabilities.^[114] Additional findings were carried out by **Gomes de Lemos et.al., (2024)** devised and characterized various Pyrazoline hybrids and evaluated them for their anti-oxidant activity and acetyl cholinesterase inhibition activity. Compounds **45a-d** as illustrated in **Figure 56 and 57**, demonstrated notable antioxidant potential exhibiting IC₅₀ (mg. mL⁻¹) of 0.4017, 0.2892, 0.1100, 0.0578, respectively. In general, the crafted compound **45a**, displayed outstanding biological activity closely matching that of standard compounds in both assays.^[115] To examine the flow of pharmacological potential, **Ali Alsalamy et. al., (2024)** carried out a multi-component synthesis and biological evaluation of novel Pyrrole derivatives and Pyrano[2,3-c] Pyrazole derivatives, as shown in **Figure 58**. The antioxidant activity of the synthesised compounds was tested utilising CO₃O₄ nanoparticles as a recyclable nanocatalyst. The results indicated that pyrrole derivatives had much better antioxidant activity than pyrano[2,3-c] Pyrazole analogues compound **46**. This increased activity is related to the structural properties of Pyrrole derivatives that contribute to the stabilisation of DPPH free radicals, as supported by the postulated mechanism.^[116] To gain deeper insights into the antioxidant potential of pyrazole derivatives, **Matteo Lusardi et.al., (2024)** crafted a series of Pyrazole hydrazones compounds and evaluated their anti-oxidant activity using the DPPH assay. The structural details are illustrated in **Figure 59** while the nature of substituents is summarized in **Table 13**. Among the synthesized compounds, derivatives **47a- b** exhibited the most potent activities. This result underscores the critical role of both the pyrazole N1 and acyl hydrazone moiety in enhancing the radical scavenging ability of the compounds.^[117] **Mohamed I.H. El-Qaliei** and co-workers, (2025) successfully synthesized, characterized, a series of azo disperse dyes incorporating Pyrazole and Pyrazolo[1,5-a] Pyrimidine scaffolds. These compounds were evaluated through *in silico* studies and were further screened for their

antimicrobial, antioxidant activities. The tested demonstrated diverse antioxidant potential at varying concentrations when compared to standard antioxidant, **butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT)**. Among the synthesized series, compound **(48b)** (reflected in **Figure 60**) exhibited an IC_{50} values comparable to BHT, indicating a similar antioxidant efficacy. In contrast the remaining compounds displayed different levels of activity and IC_{50} values relative to BHT, whereas other examined compounds exhibited varying level.^[118]

Figure 54: Structure synthesized compound 43.

Figure 55: Structure synthesized compound 44.

Figure 56: Structure synthesized compound 45a and b.

Figure 57: Structure synthesized compound 45 c and d.

Figure 58: Structure synthesized compound 46.

Figure 59: Structure synthesized compound 47.

Table 13: List of functional substituents.

Compd	R ¹	X
47a	H	H
47b	(2) Me	Obn

3.10 ANTI-DIABETIC ACTIVITY: Pyrazoles and Pyrazolines demonstrated considerable potential as antidiabetic agents through diverse mechanisms including enhancements of insulin sensitivity, inhibition of carbohydrate-metabolizing enzymes and modulation of glucose uptake. Structural modifications in the heterocycles such as aryl or heteroaryl substitutions electron withdrawing groups and hydroxyl functionalities have been associated with increased hypoglycemic efficacy.^[119,120,121] Many derivatives have shown significant *in vivo* activity in streptozotocin and alloxan -induced diabetic models as well as potent *in vitro* inhibition of α -glucosidase and α -amylase- a key enzyme in carbohydrate digestion. Some compounds have exhibited glucose lowering effects comparable to standard drugs like **Metformin and Acarbose**.^[119,121] These encouraging results support further development of Pyrazole and Pyrazoline derivatives as lead structures for novel antidiabetic agents. Nevertheless, more in-depth studies focusing on molecular mechanisms, long term efficacy and safety evaluations are essential to advance these compounds toward clinical applications. Among the recent advancements **Pankaj Kumar *et.al.*, (2021)** reported the synthesis of Quinoline incorporated 2-pyrazoline derivatives and assessed their anti-diabetic activity via alpha glucosidase inhibition assay. compounds **49a-e** demonstrated significant inhibitory effects when compared with **Acarbose** as featured in **Figure 61** with their respective substituents portrayed in **Table 14**. The enhanced activity was attributed to the presence of electron releasing groups such as methoxy, dimethyl amino and electron withdrawing groups like nitro and chloro resulted in increased antidiabetic activity. Moreover, derivatives with oxo-linkages to the 2-Pyrazoline moiety demonstrated superior antidiabetic activity compared to their amino linked counterparts.^[122] To broaden the scope of the existing review **Nagesh Vaddiraju *et.al.*, (2021)** devised and characterized pyrazoline fused indole derivatives which were subsequently examined for their anti-diabetic activity. In *in vivo* studies, compounds **50a-b** demonstrated moderate anti-diabetic activity comparable to the standard drug **glibenclamide**. With respect to *in vitro* methods compounds **50a-b** demonstrated moderate

anti-diabetic effects relative to the reference drug **Acarbose** as illustrated in **Figures 62 and 63** and the structural variations of these compounds are detailed in **Table 15**.^[123] In response to previously reported limitations, **Amina Sadiq *et al.*, (2024)** designed and fabricated 1,3,5-triaryl-2-Pyrazoline derivatives as potent Dual Inhibitors of **urease** and **α -Glucosidase**. The compounds were evaluated for their cytotoxic activity, molecular modeling, and drug-likeness profiles. Among the synthesized derivatives as represented in **Figures 64-67** the compounds **51a-d** demonstrated excellent **α -glucosidase inhibitory activity** exhibiting lowest IC₅₀ values of 212.52 ± 1.31 , 237.26 ± 1.28 , 138.35 ± 1.32 , and 114.57 ± 1.35 μ M, respectively.^[124] Building upon prior research **Ahmed M. Naglah *et al.*, (2024)** devised a new series of pyrazole-based schiff bases and evaluated for their anti-diabetic potential. A total of five Pyrazole-based schiff bases derivatives incorporating the Pyrazole moiety were designed are visualized in **Figure 68 and 69**. The structural diversity arising from various substituents is detailed in **Table 16 and 17**. Among the synthesized compounds, **52a-c, 52a₁-b₁**, demonstrated the most significant biological activity. These derivatives exhibited potent multi-target anti-diabetic effects, suggesting their promise as effective therapeutic leads for anti-diabetic management.^[125] Recent studies by **Aamer Saeed *et al.*, (2024)** reported the synthesis and characterization of novel Pyrazoline linked acyl thiourea derivatives, evaluated for their anti-diabetic potential. Among the synthesized compounds **53a-d** exhibited significant inhibitory activity against alpha glucosidase surpassing the standard reference drug **Acarbose**. The chemical structures of these compounds are depicted in **Figures 70-73**.^[126] Further analysis progressed by **shraf S. Hassan *et al.*, (2025)** reported the successful synthesis and evaluation of Pyrazole–Isatin and Pyrazole–Indole conjugates for their anti-diabetic activity. Among the synthesized analogous, **Pyrazole–Indole 54b (depicted in Figure 74)** exhibited the highest inhibitory activity against both **α -amylase** and **α -glucosidase** enzymes. Specifically compound **54 b** demonstrated significant α -glucosidase inhibition with an IC₅₀ of 2.76 ± 0.01 μ g/mL, which is comparable to the standard drug **Acarbose** (IC₅₀ = 2.45 ± 0.02 μ g/mL). Moreover, compound **54b** displayed notable anti-inflammatory potential by inhibition protein denaturation, achieving an inhibition percentage of 49.30 ± 0.17 which is superior to that of reference drug **Diclofenac sodium** ($48.75 \pm 0.04\%$).^[127]

Table 14: List of functional substituents.

Compd	X	R
49a	O	4-Cl
49b	O	2,3-OCH ₃
49c	O	4-N(CH ₃) ₂
49d	NH	4-NO ₂
49e	NH	2,3-OCH ₃

Table 15: List of functional variants.

Compd	X	R
50a	O	H
50b	O	NO ₂

Figure 68: Structure of synthesized compound 52.

Table 16: List of functional substituents.

Compd	Ar	Ar ₁
52a	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅
52b	C ₆ H ₅	4-CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄
52c	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	4-CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄

Figure 69: Structure of synthesized compound 52a₁, 52b₁.

Table 17: List of functional substituents.

Compd	Ar	Ar ₁
52a ₁	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅
52b ₁	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₅	4-CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄

Figure 70: Structure of synthesized compound 53a.

Figure 71: Structure of synthesized compound 53b.

3.11 ANTI-MALARIAL ACTIVITY: Pyrazole and Pyrazoline have emerged as promising antimalarial agents due to their potent activity against *Plasmodium* species particularly *p. falciparum* including chloroquine-resistant strains. Several derivatives have demonstrated strong inhibitory effects by targeting heme detoxification interfering with parasitic protein synthase and inhibiting essential enzymes such as *falcipain and dihydrofolate reductase* (DHFR).^[128,129,130] Structural features such as halogenated phenyl rings, electron - withdrawing substituent and fused heterocyclic moieties have been associated with enhanced antiplasmodial activity and improved selectivity.^[129,130] Some compounds have exhibited IC₅₀ values in the low micromolar to nanomolar range, comparable to standard drugs like **Chloroquine** and **Artemisinin**.^[128,129] These findings underscore the utility of Pyrazole and

Pyrazoline scaffolds in the discovery and optimization of new antimalarial agents. Building on the promising potential of pyrazoline derivatives **Yihenew Simegniew Birhan *et al.*, (2021)** devised hydrazine-coupled Pyrazole derivatives and evaluated their anti-malarial potential. Among the tested compounds, **55a-b** as reflected in **Figure 75** and **76** exhibited significant suppression of parasitemia in mice infected with the *Plasmodium berghei* ANKA strain. These findings highlight the potential of hydrazine-linked Pyrazole derivatives as promising anti-malarial agents. The study emphasizes the relevance of pyrazole and pyrazoline scaffolds in the development of novel antimalarial therapeutics.^[131] **Hani Kartini Agustar *et al.*, (2021)** focused on additional perspectives regarding antifungal effects of amino-quinoline clubbed Pyrano derivatives and fabricated Hybrid 4-Aminoquinoline-pyrano[2,3-c] Pyrazole derivatives and tested for their anti-malarial activity. Notably the hybrid compounds **56a-c** as illustrated in **Figure 77** exhibited significant inhibitory activity against the chloroquineresistant strain (K1). The compounds demonstrated potent anti-malarial activity with EC50 values of $0.25 \pm 0.03 \mu\text{M}$, $0.02 \pm 0.01 \mu\text{M}$, and $0.30 \pm 0.01 \mu\text{M}$, respectively. These findings highlight the promising therapeutic potential of these hybrid molecules against drug-resistant malaria strains.^[132] Continuation of the flow of previous research findings **Adnan A. Bekhit *et al.*, (2022)** devised Pyrazolyl- Pyrazoline motifs and screened for their anti-malarial activity. The two most active compounds (**57** and **58**) as represented in **Figures 78** and **79** were evaluated *in vitro* for their antimalarial activity against chloroquine-resistant strain (RKL9) of *P. falciparum* and both emerged as the potent members of the series. The compounds demonstrated IC50 values of 0.0368 (**Compound 57**) and 0.0946 mM (**Compound 58**) which notably lower than that of the reference drug **Chloroquine**, indicating enhanced antimalarial efficacy.^[133] Subsequent investigation by **Mariscal Brice Tchatat Tali *et al.*, (2022)** focused on the sketching of Pyrazol derivatives and their evaluation for antimalarial activity. As depicted in **Figure 80**, **compound 59** demonstrated significant antiplasmodial activity, positioning it as promising scaffold for antimalarial drug development. However comprehensive studies on toxicity mechanisms of action, and pharmacokinetics properties are essential to further substantiate the potential use of **MMV1794211** in malaria drug discovery.^[134] In a subsequent phase of research, **Andrea Spallarossa *et al.*, (2023)** assembled tri- and tetra-Substituted Anilino Pyrazoles and explored anti-malarial efficacy. Among the synthesized, Pyrazole **60e** (reflected in **Figure 81**) and their substituent functionalities enlisted in **Table 18** emerged as the most potent agent particularly against **CQ-resistant plasmodium strain** with $\text{IC}_{50} = 12.14 \mu\text{M}$ compared to an $\text{IC}_{50} = 18.08 \mu\text{M}$ observed against **CQ- sensitive strain**.^[135]

Figure 77: Basic moiety of compound 56 and their substituent functionalities.

Figure 78: Structure of synthesized compound 57.

Figure 79: Structure of synthesized compound 58.

Figure 80: Structure of synthesized compound 59.

Table 18: List of functional substituents.

Compd	R ₁	R ₂	X	Y
60e	H	C ₆ H ₅	COPh	H

3.12 MAO- inhibitory Activity: Pyrazoles and Pyrazolines have demonstrated notable monoamine oxidase (MAO) inhibitory activity positioning them as potential therapeutic agents for neurological disorders such as depression, Parkinson's disease and Alzheimer disease. These heterocycles interact with MAO-A and MAO-B isoforms leading to enhanced levels of monoamine neurotransmitters like serotonin, dopamine and norepinephrine.^[136,137,138] Substituents at the N-1 Or C-3 positions of the pyrazole/pyrazoline rings with aryl or alkyl groups have been shown to modulate selectivity and potency toward either isoform. The MAO-inhibitory mechanism is attributed to formation of stable interaction at the FDA-binding site and hydrophobic pockets of the enzyme.^[136,137,138] Given their dual capacity for enzyme inhibition and neuroprotective anti-oxidant effects Pyrazole and Pyrazoline scaffolds represent promising candidates for further development as MAO-inhibitors. However detailed mechanistic Pharmacokinetic and long-term safety studies are essential for clinical consideration. Recent investigations such as the one carried out by **Gulberk Ucar *et.al.*, (2021)** focused on the devising 2-Pyrazoline derivatives for evaluation of their MAO-inhibitory properties. Several derivatives demonstrated nanomolar IC₅₀ values indicating potent inhibitory activity with high selectivity. Among the tested compounds, significant inhibition was observed at nanomolar concentration. Notably as depicted in **Figures 82-84** the key candidates **61a-c** exhibited superior potency and selectivity in comparison to standard reference inhibitors **Clorgyline and Moclobemide**.^[139] To expand on the prior topic, **Hoon Kim *et. al.*, (2021)** reported the synthesis of halogenated Pyrazoline derivatives, which were then tested for MAO inhibitory action. These drugs demonstrated high selectivity for the MAO-B isoform. Notably, fluorine-substituted Pyrazolines had higher

selectivity profiles against the MAO-B isoform. Kinetics and reversibility experiments revealed that **compound 62a**, portrayed in **Figure 85**, acts as a competitive inhibitor of MAO-B, with a recovery profile similar to that of the reversible reference medication **Lazabemide**.^[140] Recent investigations by **Siju Ellickal Narayanan *et al.*, (2021)** reported that brominated 4-methyl 7-hydroxy coumarin-substituted Pyrazoles exhibited significant MAO inhibitory activity. The synthesized **compound 63** reflected in **Figure 86** demonstrated notable antioxidant potential, memory enhancement properties and inhibition of acetyl esterase and monoamine oxidase enzymes. These biological activities contributed to the overall pharmacological efficacy of compound **56** in the central nervous system.^[141]

As extension of this research work **A. U. Isakhanyan *et al.*, (2024)** synthesized a series of (2E)-3-Aryl-1-(4-alkoxyphenyl) prop-2-eneones and their corresponding Pyrazoline derivatives which were evaluated for their Anti-MAO activity. Among the synthesized compounds, **(2E)-3-(4-bromophenyl)-1-(4-propoxyphenyl)prop-2-ene-1-oh** and **4-[3-(4-butoxyphenyl)-1-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazole-5-yl]-N, N-dimethylaniline** compound (**64**) depicted in **Figure 87** exhibited significant antimonoamine-oxidase activity comparable to that of standard inhibitor **Indopan** at a concentration of 1×10^{-6} mol/ml. These findings support further exploration in this direction.^[142] In continuations of earlier investigations **I. Selatnia *et al.*, (2024)** explored the advanced studies to evaluate the biological properties of newly devise pyrazoline derivatives with specific focus on mono-amine oxidase (MAO)-inhibitory activity. Among the series, compound **65 (reflected in Figure 88)** exhibited enhanced antioxidant activity in the superoxide radical scavenging assay compared to standard in DPPH, ABTS, and CUPRAC assays. These pronounced activities can be attributed to presence of **two hydroxyl (-OH)** groups located at the ortho and para positions on the aromatic ring, which are known to enhance radical scavenging potential through electron donation.^[143] In a recent study, **MinseokSong *et al.*, (2025)** conducted a comprehensive review on the therapeutical applications of heterocyclic analogues in neurodegenerative diseases particularly Alzheimer's and Parkinson's Diseases. They are utilised as appealing building blocks in the construction of neuroprotective medications, and their structural diversity and plasticity allow for innovative treatments and better patient outcomes. In addition to the intricacy of the research, the difficulties encountered in the identification, development, and approval of novel chemical entities are frequently costly and time-consuming. Despite these drawbacks, traditional trial and error approaches though

costly, unpredictable and laborious are still widely applied in designing current Pharmaceutical formulations.^[144]

Figure 82: Structure of synthesized compound 61a.

Figure 83: Structure of synthesized compound 61b.

Figure 84: Structure of synthesized compound 61c.

Figure 85: Structure of synthesized compound 62.

Figure 86: Structure of synthesized compound 63.

Figure 87: Structure of synthesized compound 64.

Figure 88: Structure of synthesized compound 65.

4. CLINICAL TRIALS STATUS OF PYRAZOLINE DERIVATIVES LASTING FROM 2020-2025

While no Pyrazoline and Pyrazole derivatives have received FDA approval during this period, several compounds have progressed through preclinical and early clinical stages:

- **Darovasertib (IDE196)** is an oral small molecule inhibitor that targets protein kinase C (PKC) and is now in phase ½ clinical studies for metastatic uveal melanoma. The FDA designated it as orphan medicine in 2022.
- **Phase 2/3 Trial (DAR-UM-2):** This ongoing study evaluates Darovasertib in combination with crizotinib versus investigator's choice of treatment (Pembrolizumab, Ipilimumab + nivolumab or dacarbazine) in HLA-A2 negative metastatic uveal melanoma patients. The trial is currently recruiting participants.^[145]
- **Phase 2 Neoadjuvant/Adjuvant trial (IDE196-009):** This study assesses Darovasertib as neoadjuvant and adjuvant therapy in patients with primary uveal melanoma. Interim data presented at ASCO 2024 indicated that 75% of patients initially planned for enucleation were able to preserve the eye, with a median tumour volume reduction of approximately 47% after six months of neoadjuvant treatment.^[146]

Zelenirstat (PCLX-001): A dual inhibitor of N-myristoyltransferase 1 and 2, disrupting protein myristylation in cancer cells. It has completed phase I clinical trials and is undergoing dose escalation studies.

- **Phase 1 trial** accomplished in patients with relapsed/refractory lymphoma and solid tumours. The study recommended a phase 2 dose after establishing satisfactory safety and tolerability profiles.
- **Phase 2a trial:** Currently underway in Canada, these open-label studies evaluate Zelenirstat in patients with relapsed/refractory B-cell non-Hodgkin lymphoma and refractory metastatic colorectal cancer.^[147]

Thiazolyl-Pyrazoline derivatives: Many of the evaluated compounds shown potent dual inhibition of EGFR and HER2 kinase, with significant activity against MCF-7 breast cancer cells.

Clinical Status: Demonstrated potent anticancer activity in preclinical studies, particularly against MCF-7 breast cancer cells.^[148]

Naturally Based pyrazoline derivatives: Compounds such as diphenyl pyrazole carbothioamide 8 have demonstrated inhibitory activity against aminopeptidases (APN), VEGFR2, and MMP9 indicating potential in cancer therapy.^[149]

2-Pyrazoline Derivatives for Alzheimer's Disease

- **Mechanism:** Inhibitors of cholinesterase (ChE), with anti-aggregating and neuroprotective activities.
- **Clinical Status:** Demonstrated potential in preclinical studies; further research required.^[150]

Pyrazoline Clubbed Carboxamide Derivatives

- **Mechanism:** Potential protease inhibitors against *Plasmodium* parasites.
- **Clinical Status:** Identified through in silico studies; experimental validation pending.^[151]

5. CONCLUSION

In organic synthesis, pyrazoline derivatives are thought to be helpful building blocks for creating agrochemicals and pharmaceuticals. Several synthetic techniques were used to create pyrazolines. These compounds are important in agricultural and medical chemistry because of their strong biological effects. This review article reveals or highlights the research work of many researcher analysts from their recent literatures (2020-25) regarding broad synthetic routes and Pharmacological activity of synthesized pyrazole and pyrazoline derivatives. Importantly, Pyrazoline and Pyrazole inspired scaffolds are already advancing in clinical evaluation and these developments underscore the translation viability of the pyrazoles and pyrazolines framework and incentivize further exploration of its clinical potential. From various literature study, many novel compounds have been made and patented, but still, there are many new aspects, facts to be explored. So, it is concluded pyrazolines continue to be an attractive synthetic target and remains a vibrant and evolving field in Pharmaceutical and Chemical sciences.

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